

Conference Abstract

Ichthyological diversity in a tropical nature reserve (Etang de Saint-Paul, Réunion Island) from environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding

Natacha Nikolic^{‡,§}, Emmanuel Corse[|], Nicolas Juillet[¶]

‡ French National Institute for Agriculture, Food, and Environment (INRAE), ST PEE SUR NIVELLE, France

§ ARBRE, Saint-Gilles-les-Bains, Réunion

| Université de Mayotte, Dembeni, Mayotte

¶ Réserve naturelle nationale de l'étang de Saint-Paul, Saint-Paul, Réunion

Corresponding author: Natacha Nikolic (natacha.nikolic@inrae.fr)

Received: 03 Mar 2021 | Published: 03 Mar 2021

Citation: Nikolic N, Corse E, Juillet N (2021) Ichthyological diversity in a tropical nature reserve (Etang de Saint-Paul, Réunion Island) from environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding. ARPHA Conference Abstracts 4: e65462. <https://doi.org/10.3897/aca.4.e65462>

Abstract

The aim of this study was to test whether the ichthyological diversity of one natural reserve in Reunion Island (Réserve de l'Etang de Saint-Paul) could be established with a molecular tool, environmental DNA (eDNA). We hence filtrated the water (2L) at 10 different areas around the reserve. For each sampling area, 12 PCR replicas were performed and the identification of fish species was carried out by metabarcoding through a primer over a mitochondrial region (12S). This study showed the importance of reference sequencing databases as well as improvements through phylogenetic analyses. This first fish study by eDNA in La Réunion also revealed the coherence of the distribution of species and their habitat.

See the Poster in Suppl. material 1.

Collection : **1st DNAQUA International Conference** - poster session.

Keywords

Fish, tropical, eDNA, metabarcoding, diversity, protected area

Presenting author

Natacha Nikolic - Researcher at INRAE; PhD Ecology, Biodiversity, and Evolution.

Emmanuel Corse - MCF at University of Mayotte; PhD Molecular Ecology.

Nicolas Juillet - Past scientific manager at RNNESP and currently project manager at Ecologistes de l'Euziere; PhD in Ecology.

Presented at

1st DNAQUA International Conference (March 9-11, 2021)

Funding program

Funding: Réserve naturelle nationale de l'étang de Saint-Paul (RNNESP)

Grant title

National by the RNNESP

Author contributions

NN and NJ design the project. NN and NJ made the sampling. Spygen made the DNA extraction, DNA amplification and obitools biofiltration. NN and EC made the genetic analysis. NN, EC, and NJ interpreted the results. NN, EC, and NJ wrote the abstract and poster.

Conflicts of interest

None conflicts of interest.

Supplementary material

Suppl. material 1: Poster - Ichthyological diversity in a tropical nature reserve (Etang de Saint-Paul, Réunion Island) from environmental DNA (eDNA) metabarcoding [doi](#)

Authors: Natacha Nikolc, Emmanuel Corse, Nicolas Juillet

Data type: POSTER

[Download file](#) (1002.56 kb)